

We perform input/activation and weight quantization adapted from DoReFa-Net. The math is briefly described as follows.

Both weight and input are quantized based on an extensive STRAIGHT-THROUGH ESTIMATOR (STE) method, which is expressed as,

$$r_o = \text{quantize}_k(r_i) = \frac{1}{2^k - 1} \text{round}((2^k - 1)r_i)$$

A real number r_i in $[0, 1]$ is quantized to a k -bit output r_o in $[0, 1]$ following the equation.

Weight quantization. As weights may be positive or negative, restricting the range of weight in $[0, 1]$ could cause accuracy degradation. Instead of applying the extensive STE directly, we employ the following method.

$$r_o = 2\text{quantize}_k\left(\frac{\tanh(r_i)}{2\max(|\tanh(r_i)|)} + \frac{1}{2}\right) - 1,$$

where \tanh rescales the range of weights to $[-1, 1]$ before being quantized to k -bit.

$\frac{\tanh(r_i)}{2\max(|\tanh(r_i)|)} + \frac{1}{2}$ makes the value in $[0, 1]$, where the maximum is taken over all weights in that layer. The quantize_k quantizes it to k -bit fixed-point ranging in $[0, 1]$. An affine transform is performed to scale the k -bit weight back to $[-1, 1]$.

Input quantization. For the input layers after ReLU, the extensive STE method can be used directly, while the new method used on weights can be adapted for inputs.